

**REDUCING EDUCATION RELATED POVERTY IN NIGERIA: AN
ASSESSMENT OF BLOCK MOULDING ENTERPRISES IN
ILORIN WEST, KWARA STATE.**

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Abstract

In Nigeria, the issue of poverty is increasingly becoming threat to economic and social stability. This is particularly worrisome because majority of the people live below the internationally approved poverty line of one dollar per day. This situation hindered most household heads from sponsoring their children and wards to schools to acquire formal education. This paper therefore assessed the role of selected block moulding entrepreneurs in reducing education related poverty in the area of study. Questionnaire was the instrument used in the study. Independent T-test was applied to analyze the difference between the numbers of children sponsored to schools by two mutually exclusive groups of respondents. the findings indicated that the income generated by the heads of selected enterprises is not only capable of being used to meet basic necessities of the such as feeding, clothing and shelter but also capable of being used to sponsor children to schools-a phenomenon that leads to reduction in the level of illiteracy at least in the area of study. It was concluded small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are capable of not only reducing income related poverty but also some aspect of non-income oriented poverty like acquisition of formal education.

The paper finally recommended among other things that government should direct its "education for all" policy towards upliftment of small and medium enterprises. This will enhance their income generation capacity which will in turn enable them spend more on their children education.

Keywords:- *Poverty, Moulding, Enterprises.*

Introduction

Poverty is usually described as inability to gain access to the basic necessities of life such as food, clothing and shelter amongst others. Poverty is real and it exists in all economies of the world, though at varying extents, (Ajakaiye and Olomola, 2003). The issue of poverty alleviation has therefore assumed national and international importance after decades of its relegation to the background. Sanda, et al (2006) noted that many countries in the sub-Saharan African region have embraced sweeping development policy reforms aimed at achieving significant reduction of poverty in their respective domains.

In Nigeria, the issue of poverty is increasingly a threat to economic and social stability. Many Nigerians could not afford the basic necessities of life as majority of them live below the internationally approved poverty line of one dollar per day (World Bank, 1993). Many Children of this group of people are denied access to basic education. The effort of the government regarding free basic education has not adequately been to eradicate this educational related poverty. Generally, various efforts of successive governments in alleviating poverty among the populace through the operations of public sectors institutions had not yielded expected outcome. This calls for the need for private sector to complement government's efforts in reducing poverty and promoting income-yielding employment opportunities in the country.

This paper therefore aims at empirically assessing the role of selected Block-moulding enterprises in improving access to formal education in the are of study. Here the variable, access to formal education is used as index of human development measurement of poverty. The remaining part of the paper form this introduction is structured into five sections. Section two deals with definational concept of poverty. Section three treats issues relating to poverty measures. In section four, research methodology is discussed. Section five contains presentation and discussion of the results. Section six,

last section, takes care of concluding remarks.

The Concept Poverty

Different economists have attempted defining poverty in different ways but the fact remains that poverty is easier to describe than define. Oyejide (1993) and World Bank, (1990) defined poverty as the inability of an individual or section of a society to attain a specified minimum standard of living. Poverty is also seen as situations of hunger, lack of shelter, not being able to attend school, not having a job, fear for the future, losing a child to illness brought about by unclean water, powerlessness as well as lack of representation and freedom (World Bank, 1991). Poverty in its real sense transcends beyond lack of liquidity as it also encompasses other bad conditions that reduce the integrity and social status of human beings. Encyclopedia Americana, (1998) viewed poverty from two different angles, "Moneylessness" and "powerlessness". Moneylessness aspect of poverty manifests in the forms of insufficiency of cash and chronic inadequacy of resources to satisfy basic human needs such as nutrition, rest, body care etc. in the perspective of powerlessness, poverty could be defined as lack of opportunities and choices needed to take personal decision and this seems to make the lives of the affect people subjected to force outside their control.

Poverty is perceived in literature differently by different researchers. Where as some researchers describe the menace in terms of income (purchasing power), others describe poverty in the context of other important socio-economic variables. The study of Ajakaiye and Adeyeye, (2001) for instance perceived poverty menace in four dimensions. It could be as result of lack of access to basic needs/essential goods and services, lack of or impaired access to productive resources, inefficient use of common resources such as dams, grazing land, forestry and outcome of exclusive mechanism. This classification shows that poverty may arise either due to

shortage of income of inadequate infrastructural provision. Another notable way of conceptualizing poverty is in terms of absolute or relative. The major difference between these two categories of poverty lies on the fact that the former is hinged on the income of the individual where as the later is based on the minimum contemporary standard of living in a society vis-à-vis individuals income, (Odejide, 1997).

One of the valid generalizations about the poor people is that they are disproportionately located in the rural areas where they primarily engage in agricultural and other related activities, (Ijaiya, 2002). Similarly research document has shown that the rate at which poverty affects women is more than that of men. The reason is attributed to the customs of the land that require women to share their potential working hours between home management and actual economic job, (Anyanwu, 1997). Generally, the poor people seems vulnerable because they are susceptible to large fluctuations in real income, coupled with the absence of synchronizing mechanisms to stabilize purchasing power.

From the foregoing, we can see that poverty means different things to different people. Economists explain poverty in relations to income, in the opinion of the political scientists it is the lack of empowerment on the part of the masses. At the same time, urban geographers and sociologists would tend to equate poverty with lack of social infrastructure and opportunities in the society.

Measures Poverty

The measures of poverty are complex and varied to the extent that discussion on poverty itself revolves around issues such as simple living standard measure, poverty line determination and array of measures portraying absolute and relative poverty measures, (Ajakaiye and Adeyeye, 2001). Baye (1998) observed that appropriate poverty measure must reflect

three elements such as; the incidence (prevalence) of poverty as measured by the number of people in the total population living below the poverty line; the intensity (depth) of poverty which usually reflects in the extent to which the income of the poor fall below the poverty line, and the degree of inequality among the poor. The two broad classification of poverty i.e. absolute and relative have different ways of measuring them. Absolute poverty is measured in five different ways namely; headcount ratio/incidence of poverty, the poverty gap/income shortfall, composite poverty measures, the physical quality of life index (PQL) and the human development index (HDI) (Ajakaiye and Adeyeye, 2001). Baye (1998) observed that appropriate poverty measure must reflect three basic elements such as; the incidence (prevalence) of poverty as measured by the number of people in the total population living below the poverty line; the intensity (depth) of poverty which usually reflects in the extent to which the income of the poor fall below the poverty line, and the degree of inequality among the poor. The two broad classification of poverty i.e. absolute and relative have different ways of measuring them. Absolute poverty is measured in five different ways namely; headcount ratio/incidence of poverty, the poverty gap/income shortfall, composite poverty measures, the physical quality of life index (PQL) and the human development index (HDI) (Ajakaiye and Adeyeye, 2001).

Among these five measures of absolute poverty, the headcount ratio seems to be the simplest and most common measure considering the self explanatory attribute of its variables.

The Human Development Index (HDI) is the most recent composite index devised by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 1990). This index focuses on human development and it incorporates both income and non-income factors. Three factors notably longevity, knowledge and income are the variables of the index. Longevity is proxied by life expectancy at birth, knowledge is measured in terms of literacy and per capital income is

a proxy of income. This paper has been specifically anchored on the Human Development Index of absolute poverty. The variable, number of children sponsored to schools by the respondents is used as a proxy for non-income component of HDI.

The relative poverty measures on the other hand define the segment of the population that is poor in relation to the set income of the general population. Relative poverty is measured in two ways. The average income which is expressed in terms of the average income of the poorest population and the number of people whose incomes are less than or equal predetermined percentage of the mean income of the society (Ajakaiye and Adeyeye, 2001).

Research Methodology

The population for this study comprised all the Block Making Enterprises operating in Ilorin-West L.G.A of Kwara State. However, the researcher decide to sample only 150 Block Making Enterprises across the area of study. Random Sampling Techniques was used to select six wards/area out of the 12 wards that make up the Ilorin-West L.G.A the six wards selected were Badari, Alanamu, Ogidi, Adewole, Ubandawaki and Magaji-geri. Moreover, the study consequently adopted purposive technique to select 150 respondents from the randomly selected six areas, 25 respondents were randomly selected from each ward.

The criteria used for purposive sampling were the acquisition of moulding machines and employment of at least five workers presently by he owners/heads of the enterprises. This was based on the categorization of SMEs by regulatory agencies like small and medium scale enterprises development agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) central Bank Nigeria (CBN) etc, it is interesting to note that past researchers have worked in a similar way. Olaniyan (2005) for instance studied wood working as a component of SSEs in

Nigeria and Oni (1999) worked on auto-Technicians (Mechanics) as a subset of informal sector. A total of twenty three (23) questions were asked on a structured questionnaire which was distributed to a sample of 150 operators. The first part of the instrument contained bio-data of the respondents while the other part required information about the business activities of the selected respondents. The heads of the selected enterprises are the respondents to our questionnaires.

The data obtained from the field work were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The former was in the forms of frequencies and percentages. The later involved the use of independents T-test. This tool was appropriate because differences in the average number of children enrolled in schools between two mutually exclusive groups were involved. The tool was particularly used to test the null hypothesis raised in the paper. We should note that generalization about findings of the paper was limited to those SMEs that share similar attributes with Block Making Enterprises.

Presentation and Discussion of Results 1 Characteristics of SME Operators the Area of Study Table 1 Profiles of SME Operators in the Area of Study

Variables	Respondents' Opinions	frequency	Percentage	Total
Structure	21-30	2	1.4	142
	31-40	15	10.6	
	41-50	82	57.7	
	51-60	35	24.6	
	61 and above	8	5.6	
Hold status	Yes	141	99.3	142
	No	1	0.7	
Level of Education	Primary	31	21.8	142
	Secondary	40	28.2	
	Tertiary	51	35.9	
	No formal education	20	14.1	
Monthly Income	#15,000-#30,000	42	2.96	142
	#31,000 and above	100	70.4	
Monthly Expenditure on hold	#10,000-#15,000	3	2.1	142
	#16,000-#20,000	39	27.5	
	More than #20,000	100	70.4	
Union membership	Yes	142	100	142
	No	No	0	
Willingness of financial assistance	Yes	35	24.6	142
	No	107	75.4	
Presence of white job to SMEs	Yes	32	22.5	142
	No	110	77.5	
Business Ownership	Sole proprietorship	138	97.2	142
	partnership	4	2.8	
Gender attribute	Male	142	100	142
	Female	0	0	

Source: Field Survey, May, 2011

From, table 1 the result indicated that out of the one hundred and fourty two respondents, 82 of them, equivalent to 57.7% fall into the age bracket 41-50 thirty five respondents (24.6%) are in the age range of 51-60. fifteen other respondents, constituting about 11% are between the ages of 31-40. Also, about 6% i.e 8 respondents recorded the highest age bracket of 61 and above while only 2 respondents corresponding to only more than 1% of the total respondents fall into the least age bracket of 21-30. This shows that the majority of the respondents are adults of high maturity. This is collaborated by the responses of the respondents on household status where almost all the respondents, 141 (99.3%) revealed that they are married only one respondent (less than 1%) revealed otherwise.

Another characteristic of the respondents is the level of education. Our result has shown that 51 respondents constituting 36% acquired tertiary education either in the form of first degree, OND, HND or NCE Forty others (Slightly over 28%) possessed 'O' Level Results while 31 respondents i.e about 22% obtained primary school leaving certificate. Only 14.1% that is, 20 respondents claimed that they do not have formal education. This implies that majority of the respondents are either literate or semi-literate. As per the SME operations, our result revealed that more than half of the total respondents (over 70%) are in the average monthly income category of N31, 000 and above. The other about 30% that is equivalent to 42 respondents fall into the income category of 15,000-N30, 000 naira this particular result was also used to analyzed the null hypothesis is he subsequent section when asked whether they have benefited from any form of financial assistance, only 35 of the respondents (equivalent of about 25%) claimed that they had received one form of financial assistance or the other. The study further discovered that majority of the respondents represented by over 75% have not benefited from any form of financial assistance. The 25% that have enjoyed the assistance got it either from micro finance banks or through

empowerment schemes of local government authorities.

It can also be seen from the table that most of the respondents, about 110 of them, opined that they prefer white collar job to SME business. Only about 23% responded that they prefer government job to SMEs. This result suggests that majority of the MSE participants derive satisfaction from the business. On gender attribute, the result indicated that all the 142 respondents (100%) are males. This could be attributed to the fact that only male are engaged as workers in the Block-Making SME business and they are potential establishers of such category of SMEs.

2 Hypothesis Testing

H0 (1): Respondents with categories of average monthly income showed no significant differences in the number of children sponsored to schools currently.

Table 2 Independent T-test Results

Variable	Mena value	T-value	Sig. T.
Number of children sponsored to school	3.81		
Income group 1	5.01	-3.85	0.000
Income groups 2			

Source: Computed From Field Survey, May, 2011.

The above table showed the results obtained from the application of independent T-test. From the table, it is discernable that the average number of children currently being sponsored to different schools by the respondents in the income category of #15,000-#30,000 was approximately four while the correspondent figure for respondents in the income category of #31,000 and above approximately stood at 5. The independent T-test gave a t-value of -385, which is significant at the conventional level of one percent. This implies

that the above null hypothesis $H_0(1)$ should be rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis that says respondents with two categories of average monthly income observed significant difference in the number of children sponsored to schools. This leads to the conclusion that respondents under the average monthly income of #31,000 and above had significantly a higher mean number of children that are being sponsored to schools. In a nutshell, the income earned through SME operations has the potential of reducing income category of poverty. By extension, this same income can be said to be a good wherewithal required to attain some of human development indices of poverty such as acquisition of formal education as earlier noted. It is therefore evident from our independent t-test result that the monthly average income of the selected respondents has led to improvement in the literacy level least in the area study.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Operations of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) had a great potential of alleviating poverty in Nigeria. This is particularly so because SME businesses provide income to most youth in the area of study in two folds. First, the heads of such businesses who usually are the owners of the enterprise earn income to sustain life. Secondly, incomes are earned by workers they engage in the business. The income earned by the heads of the selected enterprises is not only useful to raise them out of absolute poverty trap, but it is also a good means to make them enroll more of their children and wards in schools. This is evident from the result of our independent T-test. Thus, the higher the level of income of SME operators, the higher the rate of literacy at least in the areas study.

Generally, it can be inferred that the two categories of average income generated by our respondents (which are above international poverty line of remember a dollar now in about N 150 one dollar per day) are capable of not

only meeting the basic necessities of life but also assisting in reducing the level of illiteracy in our land. Following the findings of this study, the following recommendations are offered.

Government should strengthen its education for all policy by intensifying support in terms of micro credit supply and provision of working tools for SMEs so that their income yielding capacity will be enhanced. Higher income that could be earned by these SMEs will enable them spend more on their children educational acquisition.

SME operators are challenged to work closely with the existing relevant government agencies to reap the benefit inherent in public-private partnership (ppp) scheme. The agencies recommended in this direction include inter alia, National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) etc. the benefit derivable from this will boost predictive effort of this category of enterprises and increase their income level. This phenomenon will translate to higher standard of living of the affected households.

The State and Local Government authorities are implored to commit more resources towards empowering small businesses owing to its poverty reduction capacity.

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